

Study of C Reactive Protein in Acute Respiratory Tract Infection in Children of North KarnatakaSneha Sanjay Pawar¹, Siddaling Chengty², Vinod Uplaonkar³, Charanraj Honnali⁴¹Junior Resident, Department of paediatrics, Khaja Bandanawaz University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi-585104, Karnataka²Professor and Medical Superintendent, Department of paediatrics, Khaja Bandanawaz University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi-585104, Karnataka³Professor, Department of paediatrics, Khaja Bandanawaz University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi-585104, Karnataka⁴Professor and HOD, Department of paediatrics, Khaja Bandanawaz University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi-585104, Karnataka

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** High C-reactive protein (CRP) values are frequently found in patients with respiratory tract infection. Elevated CRP value is a strong predictor of severity of respiratory tract infection.**Method:** 60 (sixty) children with acute respiratory tract infections were studied. CBC and CRP were evaluated, and a chest x-ray, if necessary, was studied to rule out the CRP level. The CRP level was also correlated with the WBC count.**Results:** The clinical manifestations included 58 (96.6%) fever, 60 (100%) cough, 49 (81%) rhinitis, 6 (10%) throat pain, 2 (3.3%) earache, and 11 (18.3%) breathlessness. CRP level was 0.6–18.8 mg/dl in 3 (5%) on the first day, 0.6–4.8 mg/dl in 32 (53.3%) on second day, 0.6–6.8 mg/dl in 25 (41.6%) in third day. WBC/mm³ 41 (68.3%) patients and >15000 WBC/mm³ in 11 (18.3%) patients were noted.**Conclusion:** It is concluded that, elevated CRP values are associated with severity of respiratory tract infection.**Keywords:** C-reactive protein, leucocytes, inflammatory biomarkers, RHE LAX-CRP, breathlessness.

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Introduction

CRP was first described by Tillet and Francis Jr. in 1930. They described it as a serum factor responsible for precipitation of acute phase sera with c-substance of pneumococcal cell wall [1]. It is so named because of c-polysaccharide of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. CRP is an acute phase protein synthesized in the liver in response to number of stimuli involving tissue damage [2].

Interleukin-6 (IL-6) and other cytokines such as tumour necrosis factor (TNE), IL-1 and transforming growth factors and also involved in CRP production [3]. Majority of conditions including pulmonary infection, inflammation and neoplasia through bacterial infection stimulate CRP synthesis and leads to elevation of CRP levels significantly within few hours. High value of CRP is a strong predictor of bacterial or viral infection of respiratory tract [4]. Raised CRP values in viral infection during first week may mislead the clinician in the decision to prescribe antibiotics and May also elevated CRP is observed in pneumonia after one week. Hence, it is mandatory to know the level of

CRP for every clinician there is an attempt is made to study the different level of CRP in respiratory tract disease in children.

Material and Method

60 (sixty) children 1–5 years of age who regularly visited paediatric department of Khaja Bandanawaz University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi-585104, Karnataka were studied.

Inclusive Criteria: Children aged between 1 to 5 years of age suffering from acute respiratory tract infections who have not taken any antimicrobial drugs for at least seven days for any reason. Parents or guardians of patients who gave written consent for treatment were selected for the study.**Exclusion Criteria:** Patients with chronic liver disease, congenital anomalies of the cardiovascular system, auto-immune disease, or any other inflammatory diseases were excluded from the study.**Method:** The history of every patient was recorded, and blood examinations included CBC. The

serum samples were tested for CRP by a semi quantitative method. The reagent used was "RHE-LAX-CRP." Testing was based on the principle of agglutination; a chest x-ray (if needed) was studied.

The duration of the study was from August 2021 to July 2024.

Statistical analysis:

Various clinical manifestations of respiratory tract infection (RTI) and the correlation of CPR-positive patients with WBC count were classified by percentage day of illness, and the CRP range was noted in every patient. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of males to females was 2:1.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Study of different clinical manifestations of CRP-positive patients in respiratory tract infections 58 (96.6%) had a fever, 60 (100%) had a cough, 49 (81%) had rhinitis, 6 (10%) had throat pain, 2 (3.3%) had an earache, and 11 (18.3%) had breathlessness.

Table 2: Study of day of illness and CRP levels: 3 (0.6-18.8 mg/dl) on first day, secondary 32 (0.6-4.8 mg/dl), thirty day 25 (0.6-6.8 mg/dl) on fourth day.

Table 3: Correlation of CRP levels with leucocyte count: 8 (13.3%) patients had <6000, 41 (68.8%) patients had 6000-15000, and 11 (18.3%) patients had >15000.

Table 1: Study of clinical manifestation in CRP positive patients of respiratory tract patients (No. of patients: 60)

Clinical manifestations	No. of patients (60)	Percentage (%)
Fever	58	96.6
Cough	60	100
Rhinitis	49	81
Throat pain	6	10
Ear ache	2	3.3
Breathlessness	11	18.3

Figure 1: Study of clinical manifestation in CRP positive patients of respiratory tract patients

Table 2: Study of illness and CRP levels

Day of illness on presentation	Total No. of patients (60)	CRP Range
First day	3 (5%)	0.6-18.8 mg/dl
Second day	32 (53.3%)	0.6-4.8 mg/dl
Third day	25 (41.6%)	0.6-6.8 mg/dl
Fourth day	--	CRP Not raised
Total	60	--

Figure 2: Study of illness and CRP levels

Table 3: Study of correlation between leucocytes count and CRP positive patients

Leucocytes count WBC/mm ³	CRP positive patients	Percentage
<6000	8	13.3
6000-15000	41	68.3
>15000	11	18.3
Total	60	100

Figure 3: Study of correlation between leucocytes count and CRP positive patients

Discussion

In the present study of C-reactive protein in respiratory tract infection in children of Karnataka. The clinical manifestations were 58 (96.6%) fever, 60 (100%) cough, 49 (81%) rhinitis, 6 (10%) throat pain, 2 (3.3%) ear ache, 11(18.3%) breathlessness (Table 1).

In the study of illness and CRP levels in 3 (5%) had 0.6-18.8 mg/dl on first day, 0.6-4.8 mg/dl in 32 (53.3%) was on second day, 0.6-6.8 mg/dl, in 25 (41.6%) on third day (Table 2). Correlative study of leucocyte count and CRP level was <6000 WBC/mm³ in 8 (13.3%) patients, 6000-15000 WBC/mm³, 41 (68.3%) patient >15000 WBC/mm³ in 11 (18.3%) patients (Table 3). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Differentiating between serious and nonserious infections is an important factor for the clinician. It is observed that serious infections tended to have higher CRP values; however, serious infections with CRP<5 mg/L were also found. The highest number of patients with pneumonia was also found in the CRP range of 20 to 50 gm/L. A serious infection with low CRP can be explained by the fact that in the early stages of disease, the inflammatory response is still developing and CRP is still low [8]. Raised CRP values were found in the majority of the patients with viral infections, and the highest

values were found in those with influenza A and B infections. Usually, CRP levels reach their peak during the first 2-4 days of infection. The CRP responses followed the presence of pain in muscles and joints, soreness of the throat, fatigue, clamminess, coughing, and expectoration, which, on the other hand, tended to persist while the CRP values approached normal. A minor elevation of CRP was observed in hypersensitivity to infection, and CRP values decreased continuously after the 10th day of illness. The persistence of cough after the CRP value had become lower than 10 mg/dl is in accordance with previous findings in patients with acute bronchitis [9]. The persistence of cough and expectoration may, in many cases, not reflect the seriousness of the infection but rather a post-infectious host response.

It is reported that in febrile children, the CRP value was less than 20 mg/L and the duration of disease was more than 12 hours. With no identifiable focus of bacterial infection, all children could be classified as having a viral infection. CRP values of 20–40 mg/L were recorded in both viral and bacterial infections [10,11] and most febrile children with CRP ≥ 40 mg/dl had a bacterial infection.

Summary and Conclusion

In the present study, cough, rhinitis, and fever were the most common symptoms of acute respiratory tract infections. Mean CRP levels were higher in

patients presented on the first day and decreased gradually in patients presented on the second and third days without receiving antimicrobials.

Leucocytosis could not be correlated with raised CRP levels. Hence, it can be concluded that raised CRP levels will not be an indicator for starting antimicrobial drug therapy. Such clinical trials must be conducted with a large number of patients in a high-tech specialty hospital to confirm these findings.

Limitation of Study:

Owing to the tertiary location of the research centre, the small number of patients, and the lack of the latest technologies, we have limited findings and results.

This research work was approved by Ethical committee of Khaja Banda Nawaz University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalburgi-585104, and Karnataka.

References

1. V PE Ito La, J Mertesola, and O Ruuskanen: Comparison of total white blood cell count and serum c-reactive protein levels in confirmed bacterial and viral infections J. of Pediatrics 2006, 149 (5); 721–724.
2. Higdon MM, T LE KL O Bren: Association of C - reactive protein with bacterial and respiratory syncytial virus associated pneumonia among children age <5 years with clinical infection disease 2017, 64 (3); 378–380.
3. Javadi A, Abidi P: Surveillance of acute respiratory infections among outpatients," J. Res. Med. Sc. 2015, 20 (2); 115–21.
4. Kaya Z, Kucuk Congery: leukocyte populations, and C - reactive protein as predictors of bacterial infections in febrile outpatient children Tuck J. Hematology 2014, 31 (1), 49–55.
5. Povoia P, Caelho L: C-reactive protein as a marker of ventilator-associated pneumonia resolution," Eur. Respr. J. 2005, 25 (5); 804–12.
6. Cox NJ, Subbarao K: Influenza Lancet 1999, 354: 1277–1282
7. Kulkunen I, Melon K: Inflammatory Responses to Influenza Virus Infection J. Vaccines 2000, 19 (1); 32–37.
8. Melbye H, Berdal BP: Is pneumonia a clinical or radiographic diagnosis? Aetiology and clinical features of lower respiratory tract infection Scand J. infect Dis. 1992, 24; 647–658.
9. Kim JK, Jean JS: Epidemiology of respiratory tract infection using multiplex RT-PCR in Cheonon Korea J. Microbial. Biochem. 2013, 23 (2); 267–273.
10. Mokela MJ, Puhakka J: Virus and bacteria in the etiology of the common cold J. Clin. Microb. 1998, 36 (2); 539–542.
11. Jeon, J. Rheum: C reactive protein and respiratory viral infections Korean Journal of Clinical Laboratory Science, 2017, 49 (1); 15–21.